

Eco-friendly synthesis of dendritic polypyrrole/aniline nanocomposite by electro polymerization

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Abstract : Nanosized dendritic conducting polymer composite of polypyrrole/aniline was synthesized by simple electro polymerization method using pyrrole, aniline and 4-toluene sulphonic acid silver salt (4-TSS) in acetonitrile medium. Fractal, dendrimer and compact morphologies were observed depending on experimental conditions. Growth kinetics during electro polymerization was studied by measuring the weight of polymer aggregates as a function of time, aniline, 4-TSS concentrations and field intensity. On increasing the aniline concentration, the growth rate was reduced and the morphology changed from dendrimer to compact due to interaction of aniline with growing polypyrrole chain. The radius and electrical conductivity of composite were found to depend on field intensity and attained a maximum value at critical field intensity 3.6 V/cm. The polymer composite was characterized by powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), electrical conductivity measurements, and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopic studies (FT-IR). TEM study showed the formation of nanosized polypyrrole/aniline composite with particle size in the range 47–112 nm. The surface morphology of the composite was rod shaped as evident by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). FT-IR results show the interaction between aniline and the growing polymer chain of polypyrrole.

Keywords : Electro polymerization, composites, dendrimer, polypyrrole, growth kinetics.

Introduction

Conducting polymers (CP) and its composites are important materials due to their wide industrial application^{1–3}. Composites are special class of materials originating from combination of two or more components by a suitable technique, which results in materials having unique physio-chemical properties and large potential for applications in diverse areas. These materials exhibit highly reversible redox behavior and unusual combination of properties of metals and plastics. The conductivity of a polymer can be increased several fold by doping it with a suitable dopant. Conventional polymers usually serve as the matrix, which result in special class of hybrid materials termed as polymeric nanocomposites. Dendrimers^{4–9} or other hyper branched polymers are artificial polymers with unique properties such as high degree of branching units, high density of surface functional group, nano scale size, well defined molecular weight and low-dispersity¹⁰. These features make materials attractive in many fields including electrochemistry, nanocomposites¹¹, photoactive dendrimers^{12,13}, supramolecular chemistry^{14,15}, nano-

particle synthesis¹⁶, preparation of mono molecular membranes, catalysis and drug delivery.

In the present investigation, an eco-friendly approach has been used to synthesize dendritic polypyrrole/aniline polymer composite in presence of a supporting electrolyte 4-TSS. The polymer aggregates were characterized by various physico-chemical techniques viz. kinetic studies, PXRD, TEM, SEM, FTIR and electrical conductivity measurements.

Experimental

Materials :

Commercial high purity chemicals were used in the experiments. Pyrrole (Merck Schuchardt), aniline (Merck, AR), 4-toluene sulphonic acid silver salt (Merck Schuchardt) and acetonitrile (s.d.fine-chem. Ltd., LR) were used as such.

Procedure :

(a) Electrochemical synthesis and morphology :

The electrochemical synthesis of polypyrrole/aniline

composite in presence of 4-TSS was carried out at room temperature using an experimental setup as described earlier³. It consists of a Petri dish containing a solution of monomer with and without aniline, 4-TSS and acetonitrile solution. Electro polymerization was carried out at moderate potential to prevent the oxidative decomposition of the solvent, electrolyte and the monomer. Polypyrrole and polypyrrole/aniline composite was collected after different intervals of time. Field intensity was varied in the range 2.4–5.6 V/cm. The aggregates were washed with water, dried in an incubator and photographed using 'OLYMPUS' microscope fitted with a camera. We have investigated the pattern changes and growth kinetics during electro polymerization at different time intervals, aniline, 4-TSS concentrations and field intensities. Aniline concentration was varied in the range 0.01–0.10 M whereas concentration of 4-TSS was varied in the range 0.025 M to 0.10 M. Microphotographs are shown in Figs. 1a, 2a, 3a and 4a respectively.

(b) Growth kinetic studies :

Dynamics of polymerization was studied by recording the weight of the polymer aggregates at different time intervals, aniline, 4-TSS concentrations and field intensity. Results are shown in Figs. 1b, 2b, 3b and 4b respectively.

(c) Electrical conductivity measurements :

Electrical conductivity of polymer aggregates was measured at room temperature. Results are shown in Figs. 1c, 2c, 3c and 4c respectively.

(d) Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) :

The morphological characterization of the products obtained were performed by using Scanning Electron Microscope (Model JSM – 7600 F). Results are shown in Fig. 5.

(e) Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) studies :

Powder X-ray diffraction patterns of the composite were taken in the 2θ range 0–100° using Bruker X-ray diffractometer Model D-8. Results are shown in Fig. 6.

(f) Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) :

TEM images of electro polymerized aggregates were taken using Philips Transmission Electron Microscope (Model CM 200). Results are shown in Fig. 6.

(g) Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopic studies (FT-IR) :

The FT-IR spectra of polymers were taken using

Nicolet Instruments Corporation, USA, Model MAGNA 550 in the range of 400–4000 cm^{-1} .

Results and discussion

Polymer aggregates with dendritic structures were produced during electro polymerization of pyrrole/aniline composite in the system containing pyrrole, aniline, 4-TSS and acetonitrile at different time, aniline, 4-TSS concentrations and field intensity. Results are shown in Figs. 1-4. As the time of polymerization was increased, a sharp transition in the morphology from fractal to dendrimer was observed even in a short duration of 10 min (Fig. 1a). The formation of dendrimers in electrochemical system under the diffusion limited conditions⁵ can be explained in terms of surface instability. The growth kinetics of the polymerization was investigated by measuring the weight of aggregates at different time keeping other parameters fixed. Results are shown in Fig. 1b. The growth of polymer aggregate increases with time nonlinearly. The increase in the growth rate was observed due to the continuous electro oxidation of monomer present in the medium. It leads to greater molecular mass and larger π conjugation of the growing polymer chain which in turns was also responsible for the continuous increase in the electrical conductivity of the polymer aggregates with time (Fig. 1c). Dependence of morphology on aniline concentration has also been studied and results are shown in Fig. 2a. Result indicates that the morphology was flower like dendritic structure in a circular envelop and the growth of dendrimer is divergent. As the concentration of aniline was increased, transitions in morphology from dendrimer \rightarrow compact were observed (Fig. 2a). Growth of polymer composites decreased with increase in aniline concentration. Polymerization was drastically inhibited at aniline concentration = 0.10 M (Fig. 2b). The electrical conductivity of polymer followed the same trend (Fig. 2c) due to interaction of aniline with acetonitrile forming hydrogen bond giving intercomponent complex. Addition of aniline during electro polymerization of pyrrole decreased the growth rate because of the availability of lone pair of electrons on the nitrogen atom of aniline which nucleophilically attack on the positive charge centre of the oxidized polymer and blocks this center for further reaction of growing polypyrrole chain as shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Dependence of growth morphology, growth kinetics and electrical conductivity on 4-TSS concentration was also studied and results are shown in Fig. 3. In this case dendritic structure was observed at all concentrations of 4-TSS (0.025–0.10 M). Growth rate was found to increase with increase in 4-TSS concentration due to an increase in anodic charge of the film and leads to better protonation of polypyrrole favorable for the formation of polypyrrole with large π -conjugation as evident by increase in the polymer yield (Fig. 3b) and electrical conductivity values (Fig. 3c).

Dependence of growth morphology on field intensity has also been studied in the range 2.4–5.6 V/cm was studied. Results are shown in Fig. 4a. The corresponding radius and electrical conductivity of the polymer aggregates at different field intensities were also measured and results are shown in Fig. 4(b, c). The growth attained a maximum value at the critical field intensity 3.6 V/cm and then decreased as shown in Fig. 4b. An increase in radius and electrical conductivity with field intensity may be due to increase in the π -conjugation of the polymer. Beyond this critical field intensity 3.6 V/cm, the radius and electrical conductivity both decreased may be due to loss of π -conjugation and degradation of polymer backbone.

Polymer aggregates were characterized by FTIR, PXRD, SEM and TEM studies. SEM study showed rod shaped structure for the composite different from that

obtained for pure polypyrrole having globular morphology (Fig. 5). PXRD pattern of the composite was compared with that obtained with pure pyrrole (Fig. 6). Results show that both the products are completely different. The average crystallite size was calculated by using the Scherrer's formula, $D = K \lambda / \beta \cos \theta$, where D is the crystallite size, K is the shape factor, which can be assigned a value of 0.89, if the shape is uniform, θ is the diffraction angle at maximum peak intensity, and β is the full width at half maximum of diffraction angle in radians. When applied this equation, the average crystallite size for the composite was found to be < 100 nm.

TEM studies also revealed the formation of nano sized composite (Fig. 6d). The particle size of the composite was found to be in the range of 47–112 nm, in agreement with XRD results.

FT-IR studies of polymer aggregates obtained from pyrrole-4-TSS-acetonitrile system shows bands at 1537 (2,5-substituted pyrrole), 1470 (C=C stretching vibrations of polypyrrole backbone), 1347 (C-N stretching vibration in the ring), 1167 (C-H in-plane deformation), and 908 cm^{-1} (C-H out-of-plane deformation). The bands at 813 cm^{-1} and 908 cm^{-1} are attributed to be bipolaron bands and/or C-H out of deformation of polypyrrole segments while at 751 and 679 cm^{-1} are due to C-H out-of-plane ring deformation and C-C out-of-plane ring deformation or C-H rocking respectively. The occurrence of peak at 3340 cm^{-1} is assigned to be presence of N-H stretching vibrations. In case of composite all the peaks disappeared, which clearly indicated the coordination of aniline with growing polymer chain in the polypyrrole/aniline composite.

Mechanism of formation of dendritic polypyrrole⁶ may be formulated as follows : Electro polymerization proceeds through successive electrochemical and chemical steps. It includes oxidation of monomer at the surface of the electrode to form the cation radical. The next step involves (i) radical cation-radical cation coupling, (ii) radical cation-monomer coupling and (iii) chain propagation via oxidation of extending polymer. The radical cation having greater unpaired electron density in the α -position react with the radical cation or monomer to form a dimer. In addition to α, α' linkage in the polypyrrole, some α, β' linkage can also take place. It may lead to the greater

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 1. (a) Microphotographs, (b) weight (w) versus time (t) plot and (c) conductivity of the polymer aggregates obtained during electro polymerization in the system pyrrole-aniline-4-TSS-acetonitrile at 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60 and 70 min respectively. Conditions : [Pyrrole] = 0.10 M, [Aniline] = 0.05 M, 4-TSS = 0.10 M, Field intensity = 4.8 V/cm.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 2. (a) Microphotographs, (b) weight (w) versus time (t) plot and (c) electrical conductivity of the polymer aggregates obtained at different [aniline]. Conditions : [Pyrrole] = 0.10 M, [Aniline] = 0.0, 0.01, 0.025, 0.05 and 0.1 M, [4-TSS] = 0.10 M, Field intensity = 4.8 V/cm, Time of polymerization = 60 min.

Fig. 3. (a) Microphotographs, (b) weight (*w*) versus time (*t*) plot and (c) conductivity of the polymer aggregates obtained at different [4-TSS]. Conditions : [Pyrrole] = 0.10 M, [Aniline] = 0.05 M, [4-TSS] = 0.025, 0.05, 0.075 and 0.10 M. Field intensity = 4.8 V/cm, Time of polymerization = 60 min.

random motion of radical cation, leading to complex fractal growth and dendritic structure. The dimer obtained during electro polymerization was further oxidized to the free radical. Here the electron is localized at the β -position of the pyrrole moieties, so chances of attack of another pyrrole radical cation with greater electron density at the α -position, is favored. This process would be repeated again and again with the attack at α and β positions of the growing polymer chain resulting into a dendritic polypyrrole in its oxidized conducting form.

Detailed steps of the mechanism can be formulated as follows :

In the first step, oxidation of monomers takes place at the surface of the electrode to form the cation radical. The cation radical thus obtained is further get stabilized by resonance as shown below :

The electron thus released is associated with the Ag^+ (from 4-TSS) at the cathode :

The next step involves (i) radical cation-radical cation coupling, (ii) radical cation-monomer coupling and (iii) chain propagation via oxidation of the extending polymer¹⁷.

It may be noted that when the radical cation-radical cation coupling takes place, α, α' , β, β' positions are available for coupling. Besides α, α' linkage in the polypyrrole

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 4. (a) Microphotographs, (b) radius and (c) electrical conductivity of the composite obtained at different field intensities. Conditions : [Pyrrole] = 0.10 M, [Aniline] = 0.05 M, [4-TSS] = 0.10 M, Field intensity = 2.4, 3.6, 4.8 and 5.6 V/cm, Time of polymerization = 60 min.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5. SEM images of polymer aggregates obtained from (a) pyrrole-4-TSS-acetonitrile and (b) pyrrole-aniline-4-TSS-acetonitrile systems. Conditions : [Pyrrole] = 0.10 M, [Aniline] = 0.05 M, [4-TSS] = 0.10 M, Field intensity = 4.8 V/cm.

some α,β' linkage can also take place¹⁸. This can lead to greater random motion of cation radical leading to com-

plex fractal growth and dendritic structure. This can also lead to formation of hemispherical cusps, which can fa-

Fig. 6. (a, b) XRD and (c, d) TEM images of polymer aggregates obtained from pyrrole-4-TSS-acetonitrile and (ii) pyrrole-aniline-4-TSS-acetonitrile systems. Conditions : [Pyrrole] = 0.10 M, [Aniline] = 0.05 M, [4-TSS] = 0.10 M, Field intensity = 4.8 V/cm.

cilitate complex fractal growth and dendritic structure. Dendritic tip with a high radius of curvature is more efficient than in the linear case before a plane electrode.

Conclusion

Dendritic nanostructured polypyrrole-aniline composite

was synthesized by simple electrochemical polymerization method using 4-TSS in acetonitrile medium. Morphologies were found to depend on the experimental conditions. Rate of polymerization was inhibited with increasing the concentration of aniline due to its coordination with growing polypyrrole chain. Polymer aggregates were characterized by various physicochemical techniques viz. FT-IR, PXRD, SEM, TEM and electrical conductivity measurements. TEM and PXRD studies revealed the formation of nano-sized polypyrrole/aniline composite. A mechanism for dendritic growth of polypyrrole/aniline composite was proposed.

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